

Financial Institution Support to Small Scale Industries by Commercial Bankat Madurai City

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Mr.Revanth

M.Phil, (Commerce) Scholar

Abstract

The small scale industries (SSI) have been important role of Indian economy. The essential part small scale industries canbe significant place of structure frame work of planning right from the beginning and occupies a crucial position in the industrial sector. The creation of employment opportunities, utilization of resources and income generation. The government at both central and state level established various financial institutions to provide non-financial and financial assistances to small scale industries. In the same way there are institutions in addition to commercial banks which cater to the financial requirements of small scale industries. Small scale industries can be divided into two types, namely cottage industries and small scale enterprises. In case of cottage industries the process of production will be only through manual labour in which little or no machinery will be used where as in small enterprises machinery will be used. Small scale industry encompass vast scope of covered such a activities involved by manufacturing, servicing, financing, construction etc.

Keywords: Small scale Industries, cottage Industries,

Introduction

The small scale industrial sector has acquired a prominent place in the socio economic development of our country. It is acknowledge by the government that alongside agriculture small scale industry is an important segment of the India economy Small scale industries contribute significantly to employment generation, dispersal of industrial activity to rural and backward area, ushering in all round economic growth by value addition ensuring the mobilization of local capital and developing entrepreneurial skills.

The overall credit to developing this sector goes primarily to the vision of Jawaharlal Nehru the first prime minister of free India, who proposed and implemented the development of core industry and a supporting sector in the form of small scale enterprises. The government at both central and state level established various financial institutions to provide financial assistances, to small scale industry.

Under the planned program me of rural development, rural industrialization has the major objective of employment opportunities in the non-farm sector in rural areas, especially for rural lab our, artisans, marginal farmers, women, and thereby, improving the economic scene presented the picture of a stagnant economy.

For almost all industrial products, the country depends on imports. Long term development of small scale industry was unknown. Recognizing the need to speed up industrialization in the country, the industrial policy resolution 1984, envisaged the planned development of industries and their regulation in national interest.

Operational Definition of Concepts

SSI unit

A small-scale industrial unit is one in which the investment on fixed assets in plant and machinery does not exceed rupees one crore, whether held on ownership term on lease or on hire purchase.

Public sector commercial Banks

Public sector commercial banks are the nationalized commercial banks including state bank of India and its subsidiaries operating in Madurai District.

Private sector commercial Banks

Private sector commercial banks are the private sector commercial banks operating in Madurai District. Private sector commercial banks are fully owned by private parties.

Review of Literature

Rajula Devi,(2013) in her article entitled “small enterprises for rural industrialization programme and perspective” found that the problems encountered by the small enterprises were becoming increasingly complex, and the small entrepreneurs were often baffled by a maze of regulatory measures. The woes of the entrepreneurs stem from lack of clear power perspective. A common view shared by the entrepreneurs and those who were promoters of the growth of small-sector was that as long as there was no change in the attitude of policy makers the problems would remain unsolved.

Gisha. P. mathai (2015) say that problems faced by SM’s are SME’s in India are facing problems relating to lack of credit facilities from banks, infrastructure problems, unavailability of raw materials, lack of technology, lack of training, lack of skills both managerial and technical, lack of laws pertaining to labour, competition from large companies etc. they had given some suggestions in their article relating to challenges are implementing training and development awareness programs, research and development facilities, meeting consultants etc.

Objective

- To examine the credit policies of small scale industries.
- To trace the origin and growth of small scale industries India.
- To create more employment opportunities with less investment.

Scope of the Study

The present study is an attempt the credit facilities availed by the small scale industries from commercial banks in Madurai district. The study unit consists of Madurai district Blocks. This study has covered small scale industrial units located in these Blocks. It does not cover any other districts in the state of Tamil Nadu.

Importance of the Study

Agriculture is uneconomic due to the vast landless laborers, uncertain monsoon, lack of irrigation facilities, low yield, possibility for raising only single crop throughout the year, crop failures, alkalinity and acidity of the soil and fragmented holdings. Owing to lack of rainfall and low productivity in agriculture, starting of small –scale industrial units is considered necessary to augment employment and income.

Capital, nature resources, infrastructure facility and abundant and cheap labour are available for the industrial development in Madurai district; considering the availability of such facilities in the area, one has to know about the growth of SSI sector in Madurai district.

Faulty initial planning lack of entrepreneurial skills, inefficient management practices, poor marketability and lack of motivation are that main reasons for industrial sickness. The present study tries to examine how far which scale industrial units are getting loan from the commercial banks in Madurai district.

Methodology

The secondary data were extensively used to establish the conceptual frame work of the study. The secondary data were collected from various published and unpublished sources such as annual reports relevant journals, magazines, newspapers and websites.

Period of the Study

The study covers a period of ten years from 2000-01 to 2010-11.

Limitations of the Study

This study covers the units registered with the district industries Centre It is confined only to financial assistance given to small scale industries by the commercial banks in Madurai district. This study does not cover the opinion of the officials of commercial banks.

Government Assistance

The Indian government has been supporting and developing small unit sectors. Indian is focusing on rural industries and cottage industries. According to layman's language, a small business is a project or venture that requires a small budget or is run by small group of people.

Both central and state government has been emphasizing more on self-employment opportunities in rural sectors by providing help and support in financing in terms of loans, training in terms of programs, Infrastructure, raw materials and technology.

The core purpose of the government is to utilize the local manpower and locally available resources. Which are further transformed into action by local departments, agencies, corporations, etc. The support of small scale industries

Institutional Support

1. National bank for agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD)

NABARD established by the government in 1982 to give action and to promote the rural industries. It has adopted multi-purpose strategies' in promoting in rural artisans, rural industries, cottage industries along with agriculture. Also, it sets up training and counseling plus it gives development programmers for rural entrepreneurs.

2. A rural small business development Centre (RSBDC)

The primary purpose of RSBDC is to work for socially and financially disadvantaged people and groups. RSBDC does many programmes on skill up gradation, entrepreneurship, awareness, counseling these programmes motivate various unemployed youth and young women learn different trades and introduce them to other good benefits from it.

3. National small industries corporation (NSIC)

NSIC was setup in 1995 by the government to popularize and support small businesses focusing on commercial aspects. The important functions of NSIC are:

- Supply imported goods and machine on hire purchase agreement.
- Procurement of supply imported Indigenous rawmaterials.
- Developing small business by importing their products. Supervising services.
- Awareness on technical up gradation.

Also a new scheme called performance and credit rating for small units have been started by NSIC, this ensures that the more their credit rating, the more their financial assistance for their investment and capital requirements.

4. Small industries development bank of India (SIDBI)

It is a top government bank to provide direct and indirect financial support under various schemes to meet credit requirements of various small businesses.

Performance of Small Scale Industries

Small scale industries are the second largest employer of human resource after the agricultural sector and produce a wide variety of products ranging from traditional to high-tech. SSI plays a pivotal role in the Indian economy as of being labour-intensive, helps to generate employment in rural as well as in urban areas. The SSIs had also played a cardinal role in the growth operation of Indian economy since independence despite of drastic competition from the big industrial houses and not immensely enriching support from the government. The following are some of the principal role played by small-scale industries in India to the economic development

1. Origination of Employment

The elemental problem that is confronting the Indian economy is escalating pressure of population on land and needs to create enormous employment opportunities. This problem can be solved to a larger scale by the help of small-scale industries as small scale industries are labour intensive in nature and has shown an outstanding growth in the last decade.

2. Equitable Distribution of Income

Small scale industries trigger the equitable distribution of wealth and income within societies in ways that are economically positive and without being politically turbulent, which is chiefly categorized by more concentration of income and wealth in the organized sector keeping behind the unorganized sector underdeveloped.

3. Assembling of Resources and Entrepreneurial Skill

Small scale industries can assemble an adequate amount of savings and entrepreneurial skill from semi-urban and rural areas remain unblemished from the clench of large scale industrial sector, also helps to improve the social welfare in the country by identifying hidden talents from the weaker section of the society and investing the intellectual skill for producing or manufacturing commodities. The investment by small scale industries had increased over the last decade.

4. Regional Dispersion of Industries

There has been an enormous agglomeration of industries in few metropolitan cities of different states of India. People in search of employment migrate from semi-urban and rural to these developed metropolitan cities to earn a better standard of living which ultimately leads to malicious outcome of over-populated, pollution, creation of slums, etc. Small scale industries can overcome this problem of Indian economy by utilizing local recourses in terms of raw material, investment, intellectual skill, etc., thus brings about dispersion of industries in various parts of the country and promote balance regional development.

5. Export Enhancement

Small scale industries have registered a magnificent growth in export over the years. The value of products exported by the SSIs has increased from 155 crores in 1971-72 to 124417 crores in 2004-05. The SSI units contributes about 40% of India's total export, thus this helps India in increasing the foreign exchange reserve and reduces the pressure on country's balance of payment. The data has been collected from secondary sources comprising of micro, small and medium enterprises annual reports 2015-16 and Ministry of Commerce, Government of India from the period of 2006-07 to 2014-15.

Performance of SSIs in Employment Generation (in Lakhs)

Year	No. of SSI units (in lakhs)	Yearly growth of Number of units (%)	Number of employment (in lakhs)	Yearly growth of Employment (%)
2006-07	361.76	-	805.23	-
2007-08	377.36	4.31	842	4.56
2008-09	393.70	4.33	880.84	4.61
2009-10	410.80	4.34	921.79	4.65
2010-11	428.73	4.36	965.15	4.70
2011-12	447.64	4.41	1011.69	4.82
2012-13	467.54	4.45	1061.40	4.91
2013-14	488.46	4.47	1114.29	4.98
2014-15	510.57	4.53	1171.32	5.12

Growth of Small Scale Industries in Madurai District

Year	Number of SSI Units	Employment (No. of Employment)	Investment (in lakhs)
2000-01	25813	53829	36819.2
2001-02	26968	56360	38232.6
2002-03	28175	59670	41827.3
2003-04	28917	61216	44893.6
2004-05	28118	63839	45637.3
2005-06	29921	65342	46543.5
2006-07	30013	67987	47347.7
2007-08	31080	69132	48234.7
2008-09	32632	71320	49564.9
2009-10	33430	75641	50456.6
2010-11	35460	75641	52789.3

Source: MSME

A steadily increase in employment in the SSI sector in Madurai district is observed from the data. The fluctuation in investment was found during the period from 2001-01 to 2010-11. The investment in the SSI sector ranged from Rs. 52789.3 lakhs in 2010-11.

Financial Institutions Contribution in Small Scale Industries

A successful setup, maintenance and progress of any SSI units several crucial inputs are essential for smooth functioning, this finance both for investment in fixed assets and for working capital. It is universally accepted that they are need for easy access to credit, adequate and timely need based at a reasonable rate of interest. The financial institutions in India being consistently the major source of long term funds for the industrial sector; they provide a wide variety of financial products and services to fulfill various kinds of commercial activity.

The industrial sector being small, medium or large get financial assistance to set-up and progress from this financial institution, even industries in backward areas being benefited from these

institutions which help to reduce regional imbalances. The financial institutions can be classified into two parts national level and state level institutions, depending upon the geographical coverage of their operations.

A wide range of financial institutions has been set up at the national level with the initiatives of the union government to cater to the diverse financial requirements of the entrepreneurs. Following are some important financial institution that performs a vital role in business enrichment.

1. Industrial Development Bank of India (IDBI)
2. Industrial Finance Corporation of India Ltd (IFCI Ltd)
3. Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI)
4. Industrial Investment Bank of India Ltd (IIBI)
5. State Financial Corporation's (SFCs)
6. Maharashtra State Financial Corporation (MSFC)
7. Export Import Bank of India
8. Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India (ICICI)

Conclusion

The SMEs are very helpful to remove the regional imbalances if it is establish in the underdeveloped areas. The small scale industrie are providing more employmentperunit. itscontributionistobesustained,thenuniquenessneedstobe nurturedinanoverandexplicitmanner. Theredoesnotbetwoopinionsaboutthepriority thatSMEpoliciesdeserveforachievingthesocio-economicgoalofemploymentgrowthand social justices.

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